

EVALUATION OF WOUND HEALING EFFECTS OF METHANOLIC LEAVE EXTRACT OF *PTEROCARPUS MILDBRAEDII* IN WISTAR ALBINO RATS

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ABSTRACT

The wound healing effect of the methanolic leaf extract of *Pterocarpus mildbraedii* on Wistar rats was investigated. A total of twenty-four (24) Wistar albino rats were used in this study, four Wistar albino rats were assigned to six groups. Three groups of animals (Group 1, 2, 3) were treated with increasing concentrations of the leaf extract of 200, 400 and 600 mg/kg *Pterocarpus mildbraedii*. Group 4 was treated with distilled water, Group 5 was treated with vaseline while Group 6 was treated with silver sulphadiazine cream for 14 days. Group 2 (400mg/kg *Pterocarpus mildbraedii*) indicated the highest inhibition of wound healing (100%) in relation to Group 5 and 6 with wound healing inhibition of 65.6% and 87.5% while Group 4 showed the lowest inhibition of wound healing (25%). The 200mg/kg and 400mg/kg *Pterocarpus mildbraedii* displayed significant wound healing effect at ** $p < 0.01$ compared to Group 4. The active components of the leaf extract of *Pterocarpus mildbraedii* should be isolated, identified and characterized as well as their mechanisms of

actions.

KEYWORDS: *Pterocarpus mildbraedii*, evaluation, wounds, healing effects, inhibition.

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) reveals that about a million people suffer the complications of wounds every year, thus they require adequate wound treatment. Although there are several orthodox treatments for wounds, the cost of accessing wound treatment is usually high in most developing and developed countries.^[1] Due to this, most people are unable to afford the cost of treatment and so tend to neglect the treatment procedures – thus, leading to further complications like infectious contamination. Also most of the financial cost relate to the time, cost of hospitalization and the choice of treatment procedures.^[2]

Furthermore, the conventional wound therapy currently available often leads to the formation of scars irrespective of the active components used in the formulation; and also due to the synthetic origin of most of the phytochemicals used, they often contribute to scar formation, skin irritation, allergic reactions on skin.^[3]

The size and the type of wound suffered; the existing conventional skin therapies are partially ineffective because they are only effective in a single wound healing. For examples, some are only effective in the inflammatory phase, and must be suspended when the wound is free from infection because continuous application may lead to skin hypersensitivity reactions and allergic contact dermatitis. While some therapies are effective only in the proliferative phase alone and others in the remodeling phase alone. None of these existing conventional therapy supports all the phases in wound healing.^[4]

Pterocarpus mildbraedii locally known as Oha ojii in the Eastern parts of Nigeria, and it belongs to the family Leguminosae. It is a semi-deciduous tree with a rounded crown, and can grow 15-35m tall. The trunk is 60cm in diameter.^[5] Leave arrangement: alternate; leave shape: oblong; leave margin: entire; leave venation: pinnate; leave type: simple leave. Flowers are bisexual, calyx 5-8mm long. The fruit pod is obovate-orbicular in shape and 10-12cm long. The bark is smooth, gray or pale brown exuding red gum when excised. It comprises of 60 species, all primarily used for timber and have their leaves used for vegetable.^[6]

The phytochemical analysis of *Pterocarpus mildbraedii* leaves indicated the presence of various phytochemicals including alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, saponins, and phenols.^[7]

The pharmacological activities of *Pterocarpus mildbraedii* are analgesic, anti-inflammatory, anti-bacteria, anti-fungal, anti-cancer, anti-retroviral, expectorant activities, hypolipidaemia, anti-malaria effect(s). Hence, they are very essential in the therapeutic treatments of various ailments.^[8] *Pterocarpus mildbraedii* increased rapid wound healing and the formation of new tissues (*tissue regeneration*) on wounds and inflamed mucosa.^[9]

The phytochemical composition of methanolic leaf extract of *Pterocarpus mildbraedii* possesses infinite potentials in wound treatment and healing at low cost while averting the undesirable adverse effects associated with conventional skin therapy. The phytochemicals can be used in regenerative wound therapy, as it aims to regenerate, re-establish and restore the damaged skin tissues without scarring.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Animal cages, filter paper, cotton wool, measuring cylinder, beaker, glass rod, spatula, white soft paraffin, micro-screw meter rule, analytical balance, rotatory evaporator, maceration jar, biopsy punch.

Chemical reagents

2.5L methanol, distilled water.

Experimental animals

Swiss Albino rats were procured and housed at the Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Animal House of the Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Bingham University, Karu, Nassarawa state, Nigeria. The whole animals were kept at room temperature in a cross-ventilated room, without light radiance at night to obtain the 12 hours light/ 12 hours dark period. The animals were fed with laboratory diet and water *ad libitum* and were kept in propylene plastic cages at room temperature. All animals got acclimatized after 21 days before the experiment, and they were given access to feed and water *ad libitum*.

Collection, identification and preparation of plant material

The plant leaves were collected in April 22nd 2024; at a resident in Njikoka LGA of Anambra State and a sample was deposited at the Bingham University Herbarium. The plant specimen was identified, authenticated by the herbarium personnel. The leaves were air-dried, milled to powder, labeled and stored in an airtight container at room temperature.

Ethical approval

Clearance was obtained from the Bingham University Ethics Review Committee and the protocols followed the Guidelines for Laboratory Procedures laid down by the Bingham University Ethics Review Committee.

Extraction procedures

The powdered leaves (145g) was extracted with 2.5L Methanol using cold maceration method for 72 hours. The resultant mixture was filtered with Whatman filter paper, and then the concentrated extract was obtained using a rotatory evaporator. The mixture was kept in a room temperature of 25-27°C to yield a constant weight of the extract.

Acute toxicity test

$$\text{Dose} = \text{weight (kg)} \times \text{dose (2000mg/ml)} / \text{stock concentration.}$$

The median lethal dose (LD₅₀) of the extract on the test animals was determined. Three animals were tested with 2000mg of the leaf extract.^[10] They were monitored for 24hrs for toxicity reactions. No toxic reaction or allergic reaction was observed.

Experimental Design

A total of 24 (twenty-four) albino Wistar rats weighing 85.4 – 157.7g were obtained and used. Six groups of albino rats with four rats in each group were used for this study. The trunk of the rats was thoroughly shaved with sterile razor blade, disinfected with methylated spirit and an excision wound of 1.6cm in diameter was made using a surgical blade under anaesthetized condition (Lidocaine injection). Three groups of the animals (Group1, 2, 3) were treated with increasing concentration (200mg, 400mg, and 600mg/ kg) of the leaf extract as illustrated in Table 1. Four rats in the untreated control group (Group 4), were left untreated (washed with distilled water only) during this period; to observe the wound healing process naturally without drug effect. Four rats in Group 5 were applied silver sulphadiazine Cream topically, four rats in Group 6 were also applied topically vaseline every day for 14days on the excision wound surface areas of the rats. The surfaces of the wounds were measured, as healing was accomplished and the wounds were closed gradually (except for the untreated rat). Each lesion was photographed from the same distance and with the same degree of image magnification.^[11]

Table 1: Acute toxic doses of wound healing effects of methanolic leaf extract of *pterocarpus mildbraedii* in rats.

Groups	No of animals	Treatment	Doses
1	4	P. mildbraedii leaf extract	200 MG/KG
2	4	P. mildbraedii leaf extract	400 MG/KG
3	4	P. mildbraedii leaf extract	600 MG/KG
4	4	DISTILLED WATER	5ML
5	4	SILVER SULPHADIAZINE	Q.S
6	4	VASELINE	Q.S

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RESULTS

Table 2: Wound healing inhibition (%) of methanolic leaf extract of *pterocarpus mildbraedii* in rats.

DAYS	GROUP 1 200 MG /KG	GROUP 2 400 MG/KG	GROUP 3 600 MG/KG	GROUP 4 Distilled Water (2 ml)	GROUP 5 Silver Sulphadiazine cream	GROUP 6 Vaseline
2	1.30CM (18.8%)	1.20CM (25.0%)	1.45CM (9.37%)	1.50CM (6.25%)	1.10CM (8.30%)	1.20CM (25.0%)
4	0.90CM (43.8%)	1.10CM (31.3%)	1.05CM (34.4%)	1.45CM (9.38%)	1.00CM (16.7%)	1.00CM (37.5%)
6	0.70CM (56.3%)	1.00CM (37.5%)	1.10CM (31.3%)	1.44CM (10.0%)	0.95CM (20.8%)	0.95CM (60.0%)
8	0.65CM (59.4%)	0.50CM (68.8%)	1.00CM (37.5%)	1.42CM (11.3%)	0.70CM (41.7%)	0.75CM (53.0%)
10	0.50CM (68.8%)	0.10CM (93.7%)	1.00CM (37.5%)	1.39CM (13.1%)	0.40CM (66.7%)	0.75CM (53.0%)
12	0.10CM (93.7%)	0.05CM (96.9%)	0.85CM (46.9%)	1.37CM (14.4%)	0.20CM (83.3%)	0.55CM (65.6%)
14	0.05CM (96.9%)	100%	0.75CM (53.1%)	1.20CM (25.0%)	0.15CM (87.5%)	0.55CM (65.6%)

The wound contraction % rate = $a_0 - a_n/a_0 \times 100$ and initial wound size = 1.6cm of methanolic leaf extract of *pterocarpus mildbraedii* in rats are illustrated in table 2.

Table 3: Wound healing effects of methanolic leaf extract of *pterocarpus mildbraedii* in rats.

GROUPS	No of Wound Healing	No of Incomplete Wound Healing
200MG/KG	2 (No Scar Formation)	2 (Two)
400MG/KG	4 (No Scar Formation)	0 (Zero)
600MG/KG	0 (Zero)	4 (Four)
Distilled Water	0 (Zero)	1 (One)
Silver Sulphadiazine	4 (scar Formation)	0 (Zero)
Vaseline	1 (Scar Formation)	3 (Three)

Table 3: indicates the wound healing effects of methanolic leaf extract of *pterocarpus mildbraedii* without scar formation.

Figure 1: The wound healing effects of methanolic leaf extract of *pterocarpus mildbraedii*, silver sulphadiazine cream and vaseline in rats on day 2

A (200MG/KG) B (400MG/KG) C (600MG/KG)

E (SILVER SULPHADIAZINE) F (VASELINE)

Figure 1: indicates the photomicrographs of wound healing effects of methanolic leaf extract of *pterocarpus mildbraedii*, silver sulphadiazine cream and vaseline in rats on day 2

Figure 2: The wound healing effects of methanolic leaf extract of *pterocarpus mildbraedii*, silver sulphadiazine cream and vaseline in rats on day 6 are shown in figure 2

A (200MG/KG) B (400MG/KG) C (600MG/KG)

E (Silver Sulphadiazine) F (Vaseline)

photomicrographs of wound healing effects of methanolic leaf extract of *pterocarpus mildbraedii*, silver sulphadiazine cream and vaseline in rats on day 6 are shown in figure 2

Figure 3: The wound healing effects of methanolic leaf extract of *pterocarpus mildbraedii*, silver sulphadiazine cream and vaseline in rats on day 10

A (200MG/KG) B (400MG/KG) C (600MG/KG)

E (silver Sulphadiazine) F (Vaseline)

Photomicrographs of the wound healing effects of methanolic leaf extract of *pterocarpus mildbraedii*, silver sulphadiazine cream and vaseline in rats on day 10 are indicated in figure 3

figure 4: The wound healing effects of methanolic leaf extract of *pterocarpus mildbraedii* in rats on day 14.

Figure 4: Indicates the wound healing effects of methanolic leaf extract of *pterocarpus mildbraedii*, silver sulphadiazine cream and vaseline in rats on day 14.

Figure 5: The wound healing effects of methanolic leaf extract of *pterocarpus mildbraedii* and distilled water in rats on day 14

Photomicrographs of the wound healing effects of methanolic leaf extract of *pterocarpus mildbraedii* and distilled water in rats on day 14 are illustrated in figure 5.

Figure 6: The wound healing effects of methanolic leaf extract of *pterocarpus mildbraedii* (400mg/kg) without scar formation and silver sulphadiazine cream with scar formation in rats.

The photomicrographs of wound healing effects of methanolic leaf extract of *pterocarpus mildbraedii* (400mg/kg) without scar formation and silver sulphadiazine with scar formation in rats are illustrated in figure 6.

Table 4: Wound healing effects of methanolic leaf extract of *pterotharpus mildbraedii* in rats by tukey hsd post-hoc test.

Treatments Pairs	Tukey Hsd Q Statistic	Tukey Hsd P-Value	Tukey Hsd Inference
Vaseline Alone Vs 200mg Leaf Extract	1.5502	0.8706749	Insignificant
Vaseline Alone Vs 400mg/MI Leaf Extract	1.797	0.7738416	Insignificant
Vaseline Alone Vs 600mg/MI Leaf Extract	1.4368	0.8999947	Insignificant
Vaseline Alone Vs Sulphadiazine Cream	0.2451	0.8999947	Insignificant
Vaseline Alone Vs Untreated Group	3.9957	0.0762468	Insignificant
200mg Leaf Extract Vs 400mg/MI Leaf Extract	0.2468	0.8999947	Insignificant
200mg Leaf Extract Vs 600mg/MI Leaf Extract	2.9871	0.3041365	Insignificant
200mg Leaf Extract Vs Sulphadiazine Cream	1.7953	0.7745295	Insignificant
200mg Leaf Extract Vs Untreated Group	5.5459	0.0047198	** P<0.01
400mg Leaf Extract Vs 600mg/MI Leaf Extract	3.2339	0.2258719	Insignificant
400mg Leaf Extract Vs Sulphadiazine Cream	2.0421	0.6776966	Insignificant
400mg Leaf Extract Vs Untreated Group	5.7927	0.0028931	** P<0.01
600mg Leaf Extract Vs Sulphadiazine Cream	1.1918	0.8999947	Insignificant
600mg Leaf Extract Vs Untreated Group	2.5589	0.4738073	Insignificant
Sulphadiazine Cream Vs Untreated Group	3.7506	0.1108754	Insignificant

The p – values obtained for the treatment pair 200mg methanolic leaf extract of *pterotharpus mildbraedii* in relation to silver sulphadiazine cream was 0.7745; as well as the p – values obtained for 400mg methanolic leaf extract of *pterotharpus mildbraedii* in relation to silver sulphadiazine cream was 0.6776 at ** p<0.01 as shown in table 4.

DISCUSSION

The median lethal dose (LD₅₀) of the methanolic leaf extract of *Pterocarpus mildbraedii* in rats was found to be 2000mg/kg of the leaf extract. The extract is safe and non-toxic since no acute toxic effects and acute adverse reactions were observed.

Wound healing effects of methanolic leaf extract of *Pterocarpus mildbraedii* in rats exhibited surgical wound healing, this type of wound is an acute wound (range between 10-14 days). As a result of the wound depth, the wound is termed as partial – thickness wound (because it did not affect the whole skin layers). Generally, the wound healing process is a complex

process consisting of interrelating or overlapping mechanisms of various phases including: Coagulation and homeostasis, inflammation phase, proliferation phase, wound remodelling phase.^[12] 2023).

The methanolic leaf extracts of *Pterocarpus mildbraedii* indicated increasing concentration of wound healing actions in relation to the groups treated with distilled water, silver sulphadiazine and Vaseline. From day 2, the wound healing rate of 200mg/kg of the leaf extract was observed to be quite slow; but progressively increased from day 4 upward. Day 12 marked a wound contraction rate of 0.1cm and progressively reduced to 0.05cm in day 14. Thus, from the photographic evaluation; the 200mg leaf extract healed and regenerated the original skin and no scar tissue was observed.

The 400mg / kg leaf extract displayed the highest wound healing effects (100%), the injured skin was healed completely and the original skin regenerated, restored and repaired back to its original appearance, strength and function. There was no scar tissue formed.

The wound healing rates of 600mg/kg leaf extract was below expectation due to the fact that it was treated with the highest dose of extract but showed the lowest contraction rates. Several factors may have contributed to the slow wound healing rate as none of the tested rat healed completely. The results obtained from this group demonstrates a phenomenon known as Hormesis or The Paradoxical dose – response effect. Hormesis in wound healing occurs when a low dose of a drug substance stimulates or enhances the healing process, while a high dose hinders or delays healing. Hormesis is a concept which implies that an optimal dose or dose range exists, which is potent enough to stimulate wound healing and beyond this dose; detrimental effects like delayed healing can occur.^[13] Hormesis is characterized by a biphasic dose – response curve where: Low doses (200mg/kg, 400mg/kg) stimulated wound healing, promoting skin regeneration, repair and restoration. High dose (600mg/kg) inhibited wound healing, leading to cellular stress, toxicity or other negative effects.

There are also some possible factors which may be attributed to the slowed and impaired wound healing observed. The high concentration of 600mg/kg leaf extract may be toxic to the skin cells, thus the high concentration of the phytochemicals may also contributed to the delayed healing. The high dose of 600mg/kg leaf extract possibly delayed epithelialization, thus, the formation of new tissue was inhibited and thick scar tissues were formed instead.

Excess amount of phytochemicals present in the 600mg/kg leaf extract may also impaired the synthesis of collagen, therefore possibly decreased the rate of wound closure.^[14]

Local factors and systemic factors are factors affecting wound healing generally. Local factors such as hypoxia and inflammation. Inadequate oxygenation induces temporary hypoxia and impairs wound healing, and such wounds results in the formation of chronic or ulcerated wounds Inflammation is necessary to remove all the contaminating microbes. If there is a failure to effectively decontaminate the wound, the inflammation process will get prolonged along with the microbial clearance.^[15]

Systemic factors such age and stress also affect wound healing. The delay in wound healing with age is thought to be due to decreased macrophage function and reduction in the inflammatory response associated with old age. Studies suggest stress induced alteration occurs in the normal wound healing process by reducing the function of the immune system.^[16]

The group 4 treated with distilled water exhibited the slowest rates of wound healing due to the the natural wound healing process without any drug effect. Thus, the methanolic leaf extrcat of *P. mildbraedii* healed, regenerated, repaired and restored the injured skin. Tissue scarring (scar formation) was observed with group 5 treated with siver sulphadiazine cream, from day 2 to day 8, the wound healing was slow but the healing rate was high on day 10. Vaseline (Group 6) healed the wound to an extent, but was not potent enough to restore the injured skin, therefore scar formation. Vaseline displayed minor superficial wound healing not partial – thickness wounds.^[17]

Tissue scarring is a major characteristics in skin wound healing often occurring after a skin injury.

the methanolic leaf extrcat of *P. mildbraedii* indicated rapid acute wound healing activities and prevented matured scar formation leading to complete wound healing.^[18]

In Tukey HSD Post-hoc test analysis, P – values indicates that the difference between the reference group and the therapeutic groups is not stastically significant. Therefore, the observed difference in wound healing and scarring occurred basically by chance. The methanolic leaf extrcat of *P. mildbraedii* (200mg/kg and 400mg/kg) showed a more desirable outcome, as it not only healed the wounds but also prevented scarring and completely

regenerated the injured skin. In contrast, the standard drug (Silver sulphadiazine cream) healed the wounds also, but did not prevent scarring.

The methanolic leaf extract was obtained from the plant *Pterocarpus mildbraedii*, the plant contains various phytochemicals such as alkaloids, saponins, tanins, flavonoids and phenols. The wound healing effect produced by this leaf extract was facilitated by the interactions between the phytochemicals and the receptors in the skin cells and tissues (Presenting a Drug-Receptor Complex).^[19] There is a relationship however, between phytochemicals and the pharmacological actions they induce. Alkaloids are generally known to have analgesic, anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial and anti-fungal actions. This is why; during the treatment duration, (from day 2 upwards) the rats experienced analgesia (pain relief) and the rate of inflammation was reduced.^[20]

Flavonoids contains quercetin; which is reported to have very powerful anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidant activities. The interactions of quercetin with the injured tissue also contributed in the wound repair and accelerated its healing. Quercetin is a naturally – occurring anti-fibrotic agent, and thus, diminishes scar formation. The observed regeneration of the wounded skin was as a result of the synergic interactions between these phytochemicals and quercetin to achieve the regeneration of the wounded area.^[21]

Tannin known as gallic acid produced an astringent effect, that resulted in preventing further bleeding from the wound. It equally induced a strong anti-oxidant effect which led to the activation of growth factors that are responsible for wound healing such as Focal Adhesion Kinases (FAK) and Extracellular signal – regulated kinases (ErK).^[21] Phenolic compounds present include Chlorogenic acid and 1,2,3,4 – Butanetrol. The analysis of chlorogenic acids contributed to wound healing, which enhances capillary density and collagen production effects, anti-oxidant effects and stimulates anti-inflammatory effects in the wounded tissues.^[21] Saponins is a class of phytochemical majorly responsible for the phase one of the wound healing, saponins contributed to the wound healing due to its antimicrobial activity in preventing infection in wounds.^[22]

The methanolic leaf extract of *Pterocarpus mildbraedii* repaired, restored and regenerated the injured skin area to its normal function without scar formation.

CONCLUSION

The methanolic leaf extract of *Pterocarpus mildbraedii* exhibited the concept of Hormesis and how a low dose showed better wound healing effects than a high dose of the leaf extract, this study stands out as a novel approach in wound treatment and regenerative therapy.

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